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CHINA'S GROWING PRESENCE IN THE HORN OF AFRICA REGION SINCE 2000: AN INTEGRATING PARTNER?

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Abstract

Several studies indicate that economic infrastructures play a great role in promoting regional integration. The increase in infrastructural investments demonstrates a certain convergence in advancing regional integration. To this end, this article intends to analyze whether or not China's growing infrastructure investment since 2000 has been bringing about socio-political and economic integration in the Horn of Africa. Thus, the principal objective of this article is to critically examine the nature of Chinese infrastructure projects in the Horn of Africa from the perspective of regional integration. For the purpose of the present discussion a qualitative research approach was employed, and both primary and secondary data were collected and analyzed. Accordingly, the study proved that Chinese infrastructure projects haven't played an integrative role in the Horn of Africa for different reasons: China's little commitment to support regional peace and security initiatives; lack of a clear road map regarding the execution of various projects; lack of awareness concerning the role of RECs for integration; the existence of fragmented lending culture; uneven distribution of infrastructure projects between countries; and China's greater obsession with national than regional matters are among them.

Key Words: China, Horn of Africa, Regionalization, Regional Integration, Infrastructure

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Introduction

The multidimensional cooperation between China and Africa can be traced back to the historic Bandung Conference, held in Indonesia on April 18-24, 1955 (Asnate, 2018). This historic conference shows that the socio-political and economic cooperation between China and Africa is not a new phenomenon. China has been involved in African human and economic development since the mid-1950s, but the relationship between the two entities changed dramatically with the rapid transformation of the Chinese economy, most notably since the new millennium (Alden, 2007). For instance, in October 2000 the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) was established to mitigate challenges of future cooperation. More importantly, FOCAC has served as an official platform to strengthen the relationship between China and Africa for the last two decades (Dent, 2011; Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020).

China has had a strong presence in Africa since the establishment of FOCAC. After that, China has become Africa's largest trading and investment partner. China has several large-scale projects across the continent. The Beijing Government has provided 86 \$ Billion loans for Africa over a decade to finance around 3000 projects that include highways, railways, hydroelectric power dams, ICT infrastructures, industrial parks, hospitals, educational and research institutions, sea ports, airports, stadiums, smart cities to mention but the few. Parallel to this, china has invested a lot in vital economic sectors such as energy, mining, communication, transportation, manufacturing, and service across Africa (Chuan, 2009; Dijk, 2009).

This huge presence of China in Africa has been a source of heated debate around the world. These days, commentators in the area have interrogated the nature of the contribution made by Chinese development cooperation in Africa and some other continents. The question of what role the Chinese state and Chinese big companies play in Africa's development in particular has fascinated the world. China's increasing role as a provider of development assistance, and the broader impact of its economic engagement overseas, is the subject of discussion and debate both within and outside of the academic circle (Axel, 2010; Dijk, 2009).

Accordingly, on the one hand, some scholars and Western media outlets viewed the growing presence of China in Africa as

'neocolonialism' and 'debt traps'. Moreover, these groups have presented harmful effects of the cooperation such as helping undemocratic governments to receive more power, extracting Africa's raw materials for their home industries, involving in illegal businesses, using unskilled labor that contributes to a decrease in production, putting countries in high debt that many of African countries can't afford as they are already struggling on many different levels (Dadvar, 2016).

In light of the above statements, the emerging relationship has nothing to do with the development of African countries. On the other way, Africa is losing its valuable resources like oil, diamond, gold, metal, uranium, cobalt, potassium, zinc, and the like due to the unholy marriage between these parties. They argue that in the name of development projects, China uses the newly built infrastructures as a bridge to exploit precious and abundant minerals that exist in peripheral areas. Hence, this group of thinkers believes that China has used various strategies to maximize its own government advantage without considering the interests of Africa and its people. Asante (2018, p. 265) explains this line of argument as:

"China's activity in Africa is more problematic. Chinese presence in Africa must be intensified as the scramble for resources and the process has reinforced the old patterns of trade where Africa mainly played the role of a producer of raw materials, with little or no added value."

On the other hand, some scholars argue in favor of the relationship between China and Africa. This group of scholars tends to explain China's presence in Africa in quite positive statements, even if they went to the extent of saying 'China is a blessing for Africa'. They observe that China's engagement in Africa has created a tremendous opportunity for African development in terms of creating new jobs, constructing highly demanded infrastructures, disseminating technology and knowledge, expanding the market, and serving as an alternative to the U.S. hegemony in Africa (Asante, 2018). Based on this argument, China is getting little and giving more benefit to Africa from the existing cooperation. From this perspective, China has mobilized its human and material resources for the overall economic growth of Africa (Dadvar, 2016).

The third group of scholars, i.e., accommodationists see the growing China-Africa cooperation from a win-win approach and brotherhood perspective. Accommodationist scholars argue that “as much as Africa needs China, China is also in need of Africa” (Dadvar, 2016). For them, China is improving the continent’s basic infrastructures unlocking further investment potential and leading to the creation of both direct and indirect jobs for local workers. Currently, China and Africa have equally benefited from their strong collaboration in several economic sectors. For instance, China needs Africa for its natural resource demand, and vice versa Africa also needs new technology, infrastructure, industry, and the like from China to cope with the challenges of the Western world and to realize socio-economic development (Brautingam, 2017). For instance, the accommodationists describe their claim as:

“The official policy and position of China towards Africa is based on a reciprocal model of ‘South-South cooperation,’ underpinned by equality, common development, and a “partnership of equals.” It is often argued that this aid-trade-investment approach helps to leverage donor-recipient cooperation and leads to win-win development and self-reliant development, particularly among low-income developing states. Moreover, China’s commitment to nonintervention in African domestic affairs and its determination to build partnerships based on equality and mutuality appear less exploitative and more relevant to local needs than the North’s approach to Africa and thus has tremendous potential to unlock Africa’s development prospects” (Asante, 2018, P.260).

The authors of this article believe that these controversial thoughts regarding China-Africa cooperation emanate from biased sources, the partiality of scholars, and the lack of information about the actual size and scope of China’s infrastructural investments and development loans for Africa. Accordingly, this article seeks to show what has been happening on the ground concerning the presence of China in Africa since 2000 and to examine whether China is an additional leverage of regional integration or not in the Horn of Africa.

Regional integration is a means for countries to increase economic growth and promote peace and stability. “Many have viewed integration as a tool for promoting economic growth and sustainable development and improving the living standards of the African people” (Karingji, 2016, p.4). It is about removing the physical, and

non-physical barriers to cooperation between neighboring states to address shared challenges and opportunities (Biswaro, 2013). As an assumption, regional integration creates stronger and faster-grown economies that ultimately benefit the people of integrated states. Regional integration for the balkanized Horn of African states is certainly fundamental. It plays a significant role in avoiding the human and natural barriers to free trade, free movement of people, and investment (Gaas, 2019). Karingi (2016, p. 6) puts the benefits of integration for Africa as “Regional integration remains one of the key priorities of African leaders towards achieving the African dream of continental unity and economic growth.”

In light of the above common agreed belief, Regional Economic Communities (RECs) emerged as building blocks to share some of the burdens of the AU concerning continental integration. RECs were established in different times and regions due to a firm consensus among elites, policymakers, and practitioners that the African Union alone could not bring about continental integration. This group of experts believed that continental integration can easily be achieved if RECs can integrate the countries at regional or sub-regional levels. Duma (2017) explained this line of argument as “The Constitutive Act of the African Union (AU), adopted by the African leaders, underscored the significance of the coordination and harmonization of policies between the Regional Economic Communities (RECs) for the gradual attainment of the objectives of the AU” (p. 1). Due to this rationale, eight (8) RECs, currently, have been created under the umbrella and recognition of the AU and are working to integrate their respective subregions. The Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) is one of the RECs of Africa that has been put in charge of integrating the countries in the Horn of Africa since 1996 (Byiers, 2016).

In this regard, the establishment of IGAD to harmonize national and regional infrastructure development plans has driven China to promote and support African integration by financing and building ports, highways, railways, hydroelectric power plants, clean water pools and pipelines, and ICT infrastructure. Moreover, RECs have encouraged China’s role in Africa’s regional integration. RECs claimed that the construction of regional transport networks through the removal of cross-border bottlenecks, addressing regional infrastructural gaps, and inviting foreign partners like China to close the gaps and upgrading the existing roads and railways are basic

issues that should be implemented to realize integration within a short period ((Eickhoff and Godehardt, 2022).

Even though regional integration has long been high on the agenda of IGAD, the level of integration among the Horn of African countries is shallow. Since the 1990s, which means for more than three decades, the region's governments and IGAD have failed to realize the project of regional integration. As a consequence, unlike other building blocks in the continent of Africa, the countries in the Horn of Africa are characterized by hostile ethnic groups, overly fragmented political systems, and fragile institutional arrangements (Redie, 2011).

Several studies have been conducted to quantitatively measure the volume of trade exchange and investment between China and Africa. In addition, as far as our intensive reading on the area is concerned, scholars from Africa and China have conducted research to know the socio-cultural, political, and economic impact of Chinese engagement in Africa. However, there is no detailed research that critically examines the positive or negative impact of Chinese infrastructural investments in the Horn of Africa from the perspective of regional integration.

In this context, the article examines the growing presence and engagement of China in the Horn of Africa to understand and interpret Chinese infrastructural projects and investments from the perspective of socio-political and economic integration. With the same token, the article examines the nature of China's engagement in the Horn of Africa and its implications on regional integration through China's funding and building of regional infrastructure development projects. The article further examines whether the ongoing economic and political cooperation between China and the Horn of African states supports or not the effort of integration in the region. The study also investigates the overlooked challenges and opportunities to China's engagement in the Horn of Africa. Finally, it discusses how best to engage with China in infrastructural development to facilitate the project of regional integration in the Horn of Africa.

Hence, in this study, the most important questions that need to be addressed concerning the failure of regional integration in the Horn of Africa are: to what extent do Chinese infrastructural projects match

up with the scheme of regional integration in the Horn of Africa? How did China reinforce the effort of regional integration in the Horn of Africa? The researchers believe that these research questions should primarily and scientifically be answered for further interaction between China and the Horn of African countries. To this end, throughout the study, the researchers attempt to draw meaningful inferences concerning these two basic research questions by using valuable sources that are described in the subsequent section.

Methodologically a qualitative approach is suitable to examine the nexus between China's infrastructural projects and regional integration in the Horn of Africa region. It includes context and historical patterns as an essential component to grasp the meanings made by the researcher's own experiences (Creswell, 2014). To this end, a qualitative case study was used in this discussion, with a combination of exploratory and analytical (interpretive) approaches. According to Yin (2003), exploratory research is most appropriate when the topic is new or when there has been little research done on it (Stake, 2010).

Therefore, we presented a primary and secondary data-driven view of what we know about Chinese infrastructural loans and investments in the Horn of Africa and what it means for regional Integration. The in-depth part of the present study evaluates the various infrastructural projects such as railways, roads, power pools, telecommunications, and ports that have the potential to facilitate socio-political and economic integration. As part of a doctoral dissertation, we interviewed twenty-three individuals who have experience and knowledge in the area. Moreover, we used official reports and scientific literature concerning China-Horn of Africa relations to examine the patterns of Chinese infrastructural engagement in the region since 2000, the period during which Chinese involvement in various infrastructural sectors in Africa and the Horn started to take off.

Legal Frameworks that Illustrate China as a Partner in the Horn of Africa Regional Integration Initiative

China is known for respecting the sovereignty of other countries. The concept of non-interference had been the core diplomatic principle of China, especially in the political affairs of other countries. "The principle of 'no-intervention' had been considered 'sacred' for

decades (Gu, et al (2022, p. 23). Put differently, China's commitment to non-intervention in the Horn of Africa domestic affairs has eroded gradually due to the geopolitical importance of the region and the need to emerge as an important actor in global politics. However, since the advent of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), China has been working to bring about regional integration in the Horn of Africa as one of the objectives of its government (Gu, et al, 2022; Shelton and Paruk, 2008).

These days, it's common to observe China's intervening hand in matters that are purely political by putting aside the principle of non-interference. Following the emergence of FOCAC and BRI, the involvement of China in the Horn of Africa in the domains of regional integration, state-building, and peace and security has greatly increased. For instance, in June 2022 China's special envoy to the Horn of Africa, Xue Bing officially declared China's interest in mediating the internal conflict that is wreaking havoc on Ethiopia's humanitarian situation (Gu, et al, 2022; Lynch, 2023). Xue further asserted that "China was best positioned to 'restore stability' to the Horn of Africa region (Lynch, 2023, p. 114). As a result of this policy change, China has successfully transferred itself from an economic partner to an active actor in areas such as regional integration, conflict resolution, and peace-building that need political decisions from the Horn of Africa states.

The BRI, which has been in force for Africa since 2015, has been China's major foreign policy objective since 2013. The launching of this initiative has brought China as an agent of regional integration in Africa in general and in the Horn of Africa in particular. The BRI influences China to frame its foreign policy in a way to connects the Horn of Africa countries through transnational infrastructures. In this regard, the task of regional integration would not only left to African countries, since China considers transnational infrastructures in Africa as part and parcel of the BRI. Therefore, from this perspective, we argue that since China declares itself as a strategic partner to facilitate, build, and fund transnational infrastructures in the Horn of Africa, then China should at least be responsible in part for the success and failure of regional integration (Gu, et al, 2022; Ismail, 2022). Gu, et al (2022, p. 2) explain this legal framework as:

"Of 54 African countries, 52 have already signed a BRI (Belt & Road Initiative) Memorandum of Understanding with China by April 2022, a

clear indicator that the flagship project of Chinese foreign policy of the 21st century is penetrating the whole African continent. After the BRI 1.0 phase of engagement and negotiations with local Africans and with the international community, Chinese investment patterns and sectors in Africa are poised for a major reorientation in the BRI 2.0 phase.”

For this reason, China’s commitment to build and fund Africa’s development infrastructure is interpreted as proof of China’s intentions to connect Africa with the broader BRI over the longer term (Shelton and Paruk, 2008). Horn of African states perceive the BRI as a catalyst for promoting socio-political and economic integration in the region. Such a promotion fits with the Chinese government’s intervention in regional integration infrastructures in the IGAD region. For example, the Addis Ababa-Djibouti Railway, the Kenyan Standard Gauge Railway, and Lamu Port-South Sudan-Ethiopia-Transport (LAPSSET) are examples of transnational infrastructures that the Chinese government has undertaken as part of the BRI that would eventually integrate the states that make up the IGAD. These illustrations thus demonstrate that, given that every IGAD member state has signed the BRI Memorandum of Understanding, the Chinese government is legally entitled to meddle in the infrastructures supporting regional integration (Gu, et al, 2022; Lynch, 2023, P. 116).

The State of Chinese Infrastructural Investments in the Horn of Africa

China has become the largest provider of bilateral loans and aid to African countries for economic infrastructures since 2000. Since then Chinese government and its financial institutions committed to supporting African public sector infrastructures. For instance, China gave about 153 billion USD in the form of loans and aid to many African countries from 2000 to 2019. FOCAC demonstrated that China has made a significant contribution to the construction and reconstruction of African infrastructure sectors by providing huge amounts of money (Colom-Jaen and Mateos, 2022; Dadvar, 2016).

In this regard, scholars like Zambian economist, Dambisa Moyo argued that China is a ‘golden opportunity’ for Africa to achieve continental integration as stipulated under Agenda 2063 (Calabrese, 2020). “China has already become a big source of finance for Africa’s

development endeavors. In September 2018, at the 7th Forum on China–Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), US\$60 billion was pledged in financing for Africa” (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020, p. 5). After the new millennium, there has been a significant increase in Chinese loans and aid for infrastructure in Africa (Dollar, 2016). However, the annual lending commitments of China to Africa reached at a maximum level in the year 2013 when China launched the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) (Colom-Jaen and Mateos, 2022). Dollar (2016, p. 56) illustrates this rising engagement between China and Africa by taking the subsequent data:

“Many African countries welcome China’s focus on financing transport and energy infrastructure. China’s infrastructure financing in Africa has risen from close to zero in 2000 to a peak of US\$8 billion in 2010, averaging about US\$5 billion per year in recent years. Transport projects in roads, railways, and ports constitute the largest category, accounting for about half of Chinese financing.”

When it comes to East Africa, Chinese investment in the infrastructure sector tracked back in the year 1967 when the agreement on the construction of Tazara railway was concluded by the governments of China, Tanzania, and Zambia. The building of the 1860-kilometer-long railway, i.e., Tazara, started in 1970 and was completed two years ahead of the schedule in 1975 (Dadvar, 2016). Tazara railway connects the landlocked country of Zambia to the port of Dar es Salaam in east Tanzania and is the way to export its copper to the global market. To this end, Tazara railway project has been mentioned as a pioneer for regional integration in Africa. Parsons (2021) explained the significance of Tazara on regionalism: “The rail has dual citizen and commercial use which directly boosts the integration of the two countries through freeing the movement of people, allowing more open trade, and opening the possibility of further productive integration” (p. 53).

Before the Cold War, the Horn of Africa region showed poor performance in launching and implementing basic infrastructures that enable states and peoples to interact easily. Furthermore, the available infrastructures lag behind other regions both in terms of quantity and the quality of its services. The states of the Horn of Africa also had poor financial capability to execute big infrastructural projects that allow the smooth functioning of regional integration (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020). From this

perspective, we argue that one of the challenges that affect the Horn of Africa's socio-political and economic integration is a deficiency in infrastructure.

However, since 2000 China has appeared as the major alternative to fill the budget gap for valuable infrastructures in the Horn of Africa. A key area for Chinese engagement in the Horn of Africa is financing and building several infrastructure projects. Recently, China has been known in the region for investing heavily in infrastructures, including in transportation (e.g. roads and railways), power generation (e.g. hydroelectric dams), power transportation (e.g. pools and power stations), and telecommunications (e.g. Internet). It is argued that a planned execution of these infrastructures is essential to alleviate the supply-side impediments to the Horn of Africa integration (Schiere and Rugamba, 2011).

For China, the Horn of Africa is crucial for advancing its strategic positioning towards Africa by pushing forward the Belt and Road Initiative projects in the region (Eickhoff and Godehardt, 2022, p. 2). China favors the Horn of Africa as a focal point due to the region's strategic significance on a global scale and for significant economic, political, and military growth opportunities (Ryan, 2021). That is why, unlike other sub-regions, China has given a relatively huge amount of money to the Horn of African countries for infrastructure projects. The Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, (2020, p. 5) figured out the data as:

China has disproportionately high funding in the Horn of Africa region compared to any other sub-region in Africa. With a 25% share in total finance for Africa in 2000-2017 disbursed to this sub-region. The Horn of Africa countries receive asymmetrically higher Chinese funding than the rest of the African continent, with the principal sources being the Exim Bank and the Development Bank of China. These Chinese funds for infrastructural development in the Horn of Africa have covered many sectors and also vary from country to country. The following two consecutive tables provide ample information concerning the extent of Chinese infrastructural loans to the Horn of Africa.

Table 1-Chinese Loans to the Horn Countries and Africa in millions of USD (2000-2017)

Country	USD (in millions)	% Share from the Horn
Djibouti	2,083	5.8
Eritrea	504	1.4
Ethiopia	13,739	38.4
Kenya	9,803	27.4
Somalia	0	0.0
South Sudan	182	0.5
Sudan	6,492	18.1
Uganda	2,968	8.3
Horn of Africa	35,770	-
Africa	143,349	-
Horn % share from Africa	25%	

Source (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020, p. 6).

Table 2-Chinese Loans to the Horn by Sector, in millions of US\$ (for 2000-2017)

Sectors	Djibouti	Eritrea	Ethiopia	Kenya	South Sudan	Sudan	Uganda
Transport	1,557	-	4,373	5,555	158	2,513	761
Power	-	100	2,548	597	24	2,887	1,928
Communication	18	21	3,162	74	-	10	112
Industry	-	48	2,020	-	-	180	-
Water	322	-	634	-	-	346	-
Mining	-	60	-	-	-	-	-
Other	186	275	5,375	9,132	158	3,069	928
Total	2,083	504	13,739	9,803	182	6,492	2,968

Source (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020, p. 7).

As we can see from the tables, the amount of loans and aid that the Horn of Africa countries received from China is different from one another. The tables indicated that the Horn of Africa region consists of Ethiopia and Kenya received China's financial support at the highest level, except Somalia, which received nothing from China for nearly two decades. Therefore, "The key Horn of Africa recipients of substantial loans and credits from China since the establishment of FOCAC coincides with the countries that attracted large investment projects in the sub-region were Ethiopia, Kenya, Sudan, Uganda, and Djibouti in that order" (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute 2020, P. 6). This will help us to address one of the major research questions i.e., whether or not Chinese infrastructural engagement in these countries is bringing about regional integration in the Horn of Africa.

Djibouti has been a major recipient of Chinese infrastructural loans. Chinese engagement with Djibouti has been growing in several economic sectors. For example, since 2000, Djibouti has received USD 1.5 billion from China to accelerate major infrastructure development projects. Moreover, some sources also reveal that "China invested USD 7 billion in trade and commerce from 2018 to 2020" (Bharti, 2022, P. 21). Accordingly, Chinese companies have been involved in several infrastructure projects in the country, including the Doraleh Container terminal, the Doraleh multi-purpose port, the Ghoubet salt port, the Djibouti-Ethiopia water pipeline; the international free zone industrial parks operation, the Damerjog livestock export port projects and the like (Bharti, 2022; Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020; Hussein, 2018).

Ethiopia is the fifth largest recipient of Chinese aid and loans in Africa. For the last two decades, Chinese companies have been aggressively engaged in the construction of Ethiopia's ambitious infrastructure projects. It is not too much surprise if someone says that the majority of mega infrastructural projects in Ethiopia have been built by Chinese funds and their companies. For instance, the Chinese direct loan to Ethiopia for the realization of various infrastructures reached \$13.7 billion in 2017 (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020, p.3). In addition, "By 2020, the accumulated FDI flows from China to Ethiopia amounted to 2.27bn USD" (Eickhoff and Godehardt, 2022, p. 2).

As a result, China has invested a lot in diverse economic sectors that have the potential to integrate local citizens at the national level and neighboring peoples at the regional level. In this regard, the followings are the main infrastructures built by China and that are said to bring national, regional, and continental integration: in transport sector (e.g. Addis Ababa-Djibouti Railway, Addis Ababa Light Railway, Addis Ababa Ring Road, Addis Ababa-Adama Expressway, Bole International Airport Expansion, etc.); in power/energy sector (e.g. Tekeze Hydroelectric Dam Project, Fincha-Amerti-Neshe Hydropower, Geba Hydroelectric Power Project , Genale-Dewa III Hydroelectric Power Project, Gilgel Gibe III Dam Power Project , Gilgel Gibe IV Dam Power Project, Electricity Grid Project associated with the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam, Adama Phase I Wind Farm Project, etc.); in communication sector (e.g. 4G Internet Network Project by ZTE and Huawei); and in industry sector (e.g. Eastern Industry Zone, Hawassa Industrial Park, Arerti Industrial Park, Dire Dewa Industrial Park etc.) to mention but a few (Bharti, 2022; Colom-Jaen and Mateos, 2022; Eickhoff and Godehardt, 2022; Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020; Nicolas, 2017; Parsons, 2021; Xiaoguang, 2014).

In Kenya, China has invested in several mega projects for fast delivery of public infrastructure. Kenya is among the top ten countries in Africa and the second in the Horn of Africa, next to Ethiopia in receiving financial support for large-scale infrastructures. For example, China gave \$10 billion from 2000-2017 for the construction of Nairobi-Thika Super Highway, Mombasa-Nairobi Standard Gauge Railway, Nairobi Expressway, Lake Turkana-Suswa Power line transmission station, Mombasa Port, Lamu Port-South Sudan-Ethiopia Transport (LAPSSSET), and the like (Bharti, 2022; Dadvar, 2016; Fischer and Wachuka, 2023; Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020).

Uganda also has received a substantial amount of Chinese loans and aid for the last two decades. “China has played a pivotal role in Uganda’s economic growth by providing her assistance within a framework of bilateral cooperation where several sectors such as Infrastructure, Education, Agriculture, Health, and Sports have benefited” (Allawi and Changfeng, 2018, p. 1). Among other engagements, the major Chinese infrastructural investments that have the potential to bring socio-political and economic integration include; the Kampala-Entebbe Highway, the Standard Gauge

Railway (SGR), the Karuma Hydroelectric Power Project, the Isimba Power Plant Project, and Ayago Hydroelectric Power Project (Allawi and Changfeng, 2018; Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020).

Therefore, as shown in the selected cases above, China has invested a lot and shown a very strong commitment to the construction of economic infrastructure in countries of the Horn of Africa. With the same token, Chinese companies have played an increasingly significant role in the development of integrative infrastructures in the Horn of Africa. As scientific studies, the construction of those kinds of infrastructures especially in transport, energy, communication, and industry sectors is essential in promoting regional as well as continental integration. For instance, the 750 kilometers long, Ethio-Djibouti Railway has played a pivotal role in integrating the peoples and economies of the two Horn of African countries (Colom-Jaen and Mateos, 2022; Parsons, 2021).

Similarly, if China provides adequate financial and technical support for huge infrastructure Projects like the Lamu Port-South Sudan-Ethiopia Transport (LAPSSET) Corridor that links Kenya, Uganda, South Sudan, and Ethiopia, then it will facilitate the freer movement of people, capital, goods, and services between these countries. Beyond other things, the project would have greater significance for Ethiopia, South Sudan, and Uganda i.e., the three landlocked countries in the greater Horn of Africa region (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020). In support of this claim, Parsons (2021, p. 54) argued that:

“Chinese investment can directly contribute to the regionalization of the continent. They allow for freer movement of people between nations, productive integration as firms can begin to operate transnationally with lower transportation costs, allow for greater trade between nations, and by their very nature integrate infrastructure. Their impact directly targets/addresses Africa’s greatest barriers to its integration.”

In principle, it is obvious that Chinese infrastructural investments in the Horn of Africa states would have a positive impact on the economic integration of the region. They would allow the peoples of the Horn to access reliable, fast, cheap, and efficient transportation, energy, and communication networks. Furthermore, they would

create employment opportunities, maximize income, reduce poverty, and boost the local economy. Beyond other things, the proper execution of these kinds of infrastructural investments would easily integrate the people as well as the economy of a certain region.

However, when it comes to the Horn of Africa, Chinese infrastructure investments have also been criticized for not properly integrating the region. The Horn of Africa is the least integrated region in all integration measurements. The countries of the Horn of Africa are still fragmented socio-politically and economically. The region is widely known for antipathetic relations and inter-state conflicts. Accordingly, the study will critically examine the question of why Chinese infrastructural investments couldn't realize full-scale integration in the Horn of Africa in the subsequent section.

A Critical Appraisal of Chinese Engagement in the Horn of Africa

As discussed in the previous section, since 2000, China's presence in Africa in general and in the Horn of Africa in particular has increased dramatically in terms of financing and constructing infrastructural projects in the areas of transport, energy, communication, and industry. This situation raises our expectations about the potential for Chinese engagement in the Horn of Africa to strengthen the regional integration process in the region. However, we experience a different trajectory in the region, the pace of integration in the Horn of Africa goes slowly while investment in infrastructure by Chinese private and government companies goes rapidly (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute, 2020).

As a reason that this section will properly address questions such as: why have China's infrastructure projects failed to strengthen regional integration in the Horn of Africa; and why are Chinese infrastructure investments not playing a significant role in the Horn of Africa's regional integration? One of the main purposes of attracting Chinese investment by countries of the Horn is to strengthen their basic transport, communication, and energy infrastructures to achieve deep integration at the national and regional levels. Concerning these fundamental questions, we found the subsequent responses from the interviewees, and their responses have been triangulated and substantiated with the existing literature.

The first reason for the failure of Chinese infrastructure investments in bringing regional integration is the existence of a bilateral agreement between China and the Horn of African states. All forms of Chinese business engagements and infrastructure dealings in the Horn of Africa discussed intensively in the preceding section (roads, railways, telecommunication, and hydroelectric power dams, ports, etc.) are bilateral. Colom-Jean and Mateos (2022, p. 67) persuasively explain this circumstance as “Chinese lenders may be regarded as a collection of bilateral arrangements rather than the execution of a long-term lending program aimed at supporting regional integration efforts.”

In this context, respondents such as Tages Mulugeta³, Amare Kenaw⁴, and Abebe Muluneh⁵ argued in favor of making multi-lateral infrastructural arrangements and cooperation within the framework of China- Horn of Africa engagements. On the contrary, the Chinese government has implemented bilateral engagement in the Horn of Africa as a preferred model, even if the FOCAC advocates the prioritization of issues of common concern. “China is currently the leading bilateral partner for the Horn of African countries” (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute 2020, P. 6). Chinese companies have used a bilateral approach in the Horn of Africa to minimize bureaucracies and enter into the implementation of country-specific projects very rapidly (Colom-Jaen and Mateos, 2022). The above respondents identified that this kind of bilateral engagement between China and the Horn of Africa has affected the implementation of various infrastructural initiatives that connect two or more countries. According to Schiere and Rugamba (2011, p. 21), “One of the drawbacks of China’s support to Africa is its bilateral approach with individual African countries, which leads to regional issues not being adequately addressed.” Hence, China has given less attention to regional integration issues in the Horn of Africa due to her preference for a bilateral approach over a multi-lateral approach.

The second reason is China's low desire to participate in the peace and security agenda of the Horn of Africa. As presented in the

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⁴ Director of Middle East Affairs at the FDRE Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

⁵ Director of IGAD Security Sector Program (IGAD SSP) at IGAD Head of Mission to Ethiopia.

preceding section, China has invested a lot but has shown little commitment in realizing long-lasting peace and security in the Horn of Africa. As we observed from the history of century-old engagement, China wasn't ready to put forward peace and security initiatives in the Horn of Africa. However, the Horn of Africa region is severely affected by intra and inter-state wars, political instability, violent extremism, terrorism, piracy, drought, human trafficking, and migration. The existence of these situations in the region has prevented Chinese infrastructural investments from creating socio-political and economic integration (Eickhoff and Godehardt, 2022). Concerning this assertion, the following specific cases that happened in Kenya and Ethiopia respectively can be mentioned as ideal examples:

“Chinese-operated construction sites in Lamu County—a major venue of the Lamu Port-South Sudan-Ethiopia (LAPSSET) regional transport corridor project in Kenya, which is part of the BRI—have repeatedly come under attack by militant groups connected to Al-Shabaab. In Ethiopia, fighting in the Tigray Region has forced China to evacuate its nationals, mainly construction workers. Similar to other regions in the world, Chinese nationals have increasingly become victims of attacks and kidnappings” (Eickhoff and Godehardt, 2022, p. 3).

China has been criticized for not effectively addressing these and other unmentioned peace and security threats in the wider Horn of Africa region. As such, two anonymous experts one from the FDRE Ministry of Trade and Regional Integration and the other from the Embassy of Kenya in Ethiopia said that due to the recurrent conflicts and security threats they have faced with the challenge of using Chinese infrastructure projects to advance the regional integration agenda in the Horn of Africa. Moreover, Abebe Muluneh⁶ argued that China should focus mainly on peace and security issues in the Horn of Africa to use its infrastructure investment as a vehicle for regional integration.

The third reason identified by Kathryn Langat⁷ for the slow pace of regional integration in the Horn of Africa is the lack of a clear road

⁶ Director of IGAD Security Sector Program (IGAD SSP) at IGAD Head of Mission to Ethiopia.

⁷ Research and Training Officer at IGAD IGAD Head of Mission to Ethiopia.

map or specific action plan on the side of China and the host country. Kathryn strongly insisted on the importance of a detailed and implementable plan to manipulate Chinese infrastructures for regional integration. However, Chinese officials and investors have propagated a lot about the implementation of important infrastructural projects in the Horn of Africa without crafting specific action plans. Colom-Jaen and Mateos, (2022) supported this occurrence in the region as “despite the significant amount of investment allocated to economic infrastructure by private and public Chinese economic actors in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda, there is no explicit and coordinated planning” (p. 67).

For instance, due to a blurred road map and strategy, recently Uganda decided to take a major railway project from China and give it to Turkey. This is because the project was delayed for two years and did not have a specific action plan. As a result, the Ugandan government abandoned Chinese investment contractors and turned to Turkey to build a new railway line to Kenya, linking Uganda with neighboring countries such as South Sudan, Rwanda, the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Burundi, and Ethiopia. (Fischer and Wachuka, 2023).

The fourth reason suggested by Asmamaw Kelemu⁸ and Himanot Eshetu⁹ for the failure of regional integration in the Horn of Africa is China’s weak engagement with sub-continental organizations. According to these respondents, China frequently engages with the African Union on various development issues by ignoring Regional Economic Communities (RECs) such as AMU, COMESA, ECOWAS, EAC, SADC, CEN-SAD, and IGAD. Often some Chinese aid goes to AU. For example, China spent 250 million dollars to build the headquarters of the African Union in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. China doesn’t have a significant history of assisting African sub-continental organizations.

However, Asmamaw and Himanot claimed that continental integration cannot be realized without successfully integrating countries at the regional level. So, RECs should be considered as instruments to achieve socio-political and economic integration at a

⁸ Guest professor at Addis Ababa University and, Former Ambassador of Ethiopia in Somalia.

⁹ Director of Multilateral Cooperation at the FDRE Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

regional level. China's infrastructure investments in the Horn of Africa have failed to bring integration because the government of China has been carrying out various projects without supporting and consulting IGAD as a regional organization. More importantly, they said that China doesn't have a clear strategy for citizen-centered bottom-up economic integration and institutional-oriented top-down capacity building.

China's decentralized lending and aid delivery process can be considered as a fifth reason for the minimum contribution of China's infrastructures for regionalization in the Horn of Africa. Amare and Tages identified the involvement of multiple Chinese-leading intuitions as one of the key challenges in realizing regional integration in the Horn of Africa. To be precise, "Chinese Investments are fragmented across several government institutions, including the China Development Bank, China EXIM Bank, and the Ministry of Commerce" (Schiere and Rugamba, 2011, p. 16). All these Chinese financial institutions have given money in the name of infrastructure building for the governments in the Horn of Africa in separate ways. Hence, Amare and Tages believed that the lack of coordination between these Chinese financial institutions has affected the task of linking infrastructures in line with regional integration objectives.

Kathryn and an anonymous respondent at the Embassy of Kenya in Ethiopia stated China's uneven distribution of infrastructure projects in the Horn of Africa as a sixth reason for the failure of integration in the region. For them, China has distributed its infrastructure projects unfairly across countries of the Horn of Africa. The existence of this unequal access to China's infrastructural loans and aid affects the pace of the regional integration process in the Horn of Africa. Certainly, China usually invests in countries that have relative stability and willingness to implement the Beijing consensus. For example, "The Ethiopian government sees itself as crucial to Chinese interests in East Africa. Similarly, Beijing sees Ethiopia as a nucleus for the Belt and Road Initiative and thus has heavily invested in it to earn its goodwill" (Ryan, 2021, P. 2). To the contrary, despite its diplomatic presence in Somalia since 1960, China didn't provide a significant contribution to state recovery and infrastructure projects in Somalia. Thus, this infrastructure imbalance across countries in the Horn of Africa ultimately hampers the progress of economic integration (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute 2020).

According to Abebe, Asmamaw, and Himanot, the focus of Chinese-backed infrastructural projects on national interests rather than a common regional agenda is considered the last but not the least reason for the failure of integration in the Horn of Africa. As shown earlier, the majority of China's infrastructure projects in the Horn of Africa aim to fulfill the needs of national governments. For this, respondents appealed that China should construct huge infrastructures that have the potential to give cross-border services and solve shared problems. For instance, except few infrastructures such as the Addis Ababa-Djibouti railway, Ethio-Djibouti water pipeline, and LAPSSSET, China has built several dams, roads, and ports in the Horn of Africa to satisfy only the needs of local people. However, power pools, railways, roads, and telecommunications should be built in a way that meets the needs of neighboring states to support the regional integration project. The limitation in the scope and depth of infrastructural projects in the Horn of Africa slows down the progress of regional integration. Therefore, national governments in the Horn of Africa must prove that China's infrastructure investments are associated with long-term regional integration strategies.

Concluding Remarks

Regional integration initiatives have always been part of the Horn of Africa's development strategies since the inception of IGAD in 1986. It is important to keep in mind that the economic infrastructure projects are drivers of regional integration in the Horn of Africa. In this regard, the study intensively examined the impacts of Chinese infrastructural investments on the process of regional integration in the Horn of African countries. It deeply examines the correlation between China's investment efforts and the Horn of African regional integration agendas.

Since 2000, China has emerged as the main option to fill the budget gap for important infrastructure in the Horn of Africa. A key area of Chinese involvement in the Horn of Africa is in the financing and construction of numerous infrastructure projects. Recently, China has been known in the region for investing heavily in infrastructures that ameliorate regional integration such as highways, railways, hydroelectric power dams, power stations, mobile networks, internet, and the like. Without a doubt, well-thought-out implementation of

these infrastructures is necessary to reduce supply-side barriers to Horn of Africa integration.

However, with all these Chinese infrastructural investments, the Horn of Africa region couldn't show any progress in terms of socio-political as well as economic integration. For example, concerning economic integration, the initial phases to be realized are Preferential Trade Area and Customs Union. Under these phases member states are expected to avoid tariff and non-tariff barriers, harmonize customs duties, and consolidate sectorial integration. However, this level of integration in the Horn of Africa is still far from being observed even if China continues infrastructural investments in the region. The level of inter-state trade exchange is found at an infant stage (Horn Economic and Social Policy Institute 2020). As researchers, the main challenge preventing deeper regional socio-political and economic integration in Africa and elsewhere is the lack of appropriate infrastructures. But, the puzzle in the Horn of Africa region is that the regional integration process couldn't reach at the expected level, while China has been investing a lot in key economic sectors since the establishment of the FOCAC in 2000.

Accordingly, the researchers inferred the following reasons from key informants and literature in the field to explain the question of why Chinese infrastructural projects couldn't bring the expected socio-political and economic integration in the Horn of Africa. First, the existence of a bilateral agreement between China and the Horn of Africa states. Second, China's little commitment in supporting regional peace and security initiatives. Third, lack of a clear road map or specific action plan regarding the execution of various infrastructure projects. Fourth, lack of awareness concerning the role of Regional Economic Communities (RECs) for integration. China's frequent engagement with the African Union by sidestepping the regional organization, i.e., IGAD is directly responsible for integration. Fifth, China's disorganized or fragmented lending culture. Sixth, China's uneven distribution of infrastructure projects to the countries Horn of Africa. Seventh, China's obsession with national rather than regional issues.

In a nutshell, the researchers recommend the following to policymakers and practitioners to manipulate Chinese infrastructural projects to advance the integration of all sorts in the Horn of Africa. First, China should adopt a strategy of bottom-up citizen-oriented

economic integration and institutional-oriented top-down capacity-building. Second, the industries that China needs to build in the Horn of Africa should not be identical but mutually supportive. They should be made to seek each other's input. China should focus on economic complementarities that would be conducive to cross-border trade. Third, China should support core or hegemonic states that strategically lead the integration process in the Horn of Africa. Fourth, China should develop a multi-lateral engagement in the Horn of Africa. Fifth, China should give some infrastructure contracts to local companies. Sixth, China should play an important role in the private sector than the government in the Horn of Africa. Last, but not least, China should follow a people-centered approach rather than an elite-centered in the region.

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